

THE ROLE OF THE PRIVATE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT IN POVERTY REDUCTION IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Rahmonaliyev Ortiqali Baxodir o'g'li
Farg'ona Davlat universiteti magistranti

Annotation: *What can governments do to support the creation and expansion of companies that are financially, economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable?*

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The role of private enterprise in development has been neglected by scholars, governments, and aid organizations. This is regrettable: a vibrant private sector generates jobs, raises incomes, and makes better, cheaper goods and services available.

Guy Pfeffermann

Besides improving health care, education, and macroeconomic conditions, and encouraging competition, governments can undertake institutional reforms that, over time, lower the costs of doing business and thus create a more favorable business environment. Such reforms encourage activities not only by foreign investors but also—and more important—by the thousands of local entrepreneurs who want to start or expand small businesses in agriculture, services, and manufacturing.

A number of enterprise surveys and other analytical work linking institutional factors and economic performance have been carried out in recent years. These analyses pinpoint areas in which reform is urgently needed in many developing countries. Among the findings are the following:

- A strong relationship exists between the quality of the business environment and long-term national economic performance, including the pace of poverty reduction.
- Enforcement of the rule of law—in particular, the extent to which governments enforce contracts between private parties (and between private parties and the state)—is crucial to long-term development and, as already noted, affects the poor as well as affluent members of society.
- Respect for property rights (especially those of the poor) is highly correlated with long-term economic and social progress.
- The efficiency of government in delivering services is also associated with economic progress.

In particular, a recent worldwide survey of 10,000 enterprises carried out during 2000 and 2020 under the leadership of the World Bank Group points to the leading

obstacles to doing business identified by business managers and owners in developing countries. Constraints were ranked in order of perceived seriousness on a scale of 1 ("no obstacle") to 4 ("major obstacle"). The average score for perceived obstacles is, unsurprisingly, higher in developing countries (2.6) than in industrial countries (1.95). The developing country list of obstacles is topped by four items scoring an average of 2.9: taxes and regulations, financing difficulties, inflation, and political instability or uncertainty. The next most serious perceived obstacles—corruption, exchange rate problems, and "street crime, disorder, and theft"—score an average of 2.6. Analysis of these survey data for all countries suggests that investment and economic growth are related to certain key indicators of the quality of the investment climate. For example, foreign direct investment flows are positively associated with economic predictability and predictability of changes in law and legislation, and negatively associated with constraints imposed by taxes and regulations and exchange rate instability. Likewise, GDP growth within each of the regional groupings of countries is negatively associated with the severity of constraints imposed by taxes and regulations in general and, specifically, high tax rates, tax administration, and business-registration procedures.

More broadly, the pace of long-term economic progress is intimately related to the costs of doing business. So, for example, some Central Asian countries have developed successfully in part because it is cheaper to ship manufacturing components by air to the east coast of the United States via Singapore than it is to ship the same components from the Caribbean, even though the Caribbean is much closer. Air freight from Singapore is extremely competitive, while governments in the Caribbean have restrictions on shipping capacity. In short, governments that improve institutions and welcome competition enhance the poverty-reducing impact of private firms.

The small companies—and start-up firms, in particular—that are crucial to long-term economic and social development are especially vulnerable to bad government (Weder and Schiffer, forthcoming). Poor policies and weak institutions hurt these companies more than they do others. Larger firms can better afford to protect themselves, even though protection comes at a cost. For smaller firms, "exiting" into the unregistered informal sector is often the only refuge. By discouraging enterprise creation and forcing small firms to go underground, many governments limit job creation and chances for upward social mobility. Furthermore, start-up and small enterprises are the seedbed of the middle class; the weakness of the middle class in the majority of low-income countries hampers economic and social progress.

Surprisingly, business environment surveys have not been used systematically by governments and international organizations until recently, yet they map out in considerable detail "where the shoe pinches" and what concrete steps could be taken to enhance the developmental and poverty-reducing impact of private firms. Indeed, international institutions providing financial assistance to developing countries might find sectoral adjustment loans designed to improve business environments to be useful

tools in poverty reduction. Such loans would support governments willing and able to invigorate their economies by taking on vested interests and so give more people opportunities to escape from poverty. Indeed, the steps required to improve the business environment offer a practical framework for examining the particular development challenges faced by individual countries. They therefore constitute an essential component of a holistic approach to development, along with macroeconomic and social policy agendas.

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